

Polycyclic Compounds. Part II. Synthesis of Sesquiterpene Compounds

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Action of sodium on ethyl 5-isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate(V) is described. The six-ring¹ β -oxo-ester (II), so formed on ring extension with 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one methiodide, according to the known procedure², affords chiefly ethyl 8-isopropyl-2-oxo-2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10-octahydronaphthalene-5-carboxylate (VI).

Preparation of β -oxo-ester (II) in moderate quantity was required in connection with the synthesis of the naphthoic acid³ (I). The following method has been found to be a general one, furnishing good yields.

Ethyl 5-isopropylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate(III) on alkylation with ethyl bromoacetate, followed by ring fission⁴ in presence of a catalytic quantity of sodium ethylate, afforded ethyl 5-isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate(V). The latter on Dieckmann cyclisation with sodium dust formed ethyl 6-isopropylcyclohexanone-2,3-dicarboxylate (II). The β -oxo ester (II) on alkylation with 4-diethylaminobutan-2-one methiodide, followed by hydrolysis and esterification, afforded (VI) in moderate quantity.

(I)

(II)

(VI)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

1. Dutta *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 385; Barton *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2907; George and Wright, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 1200; Djerassi *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, **81**, 4997.
2. Wilds and Shunk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 469; Robinson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 56; Wilds *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, **17**, 1152.
3. Ruzicka, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, **5**, 345.
4. Ruzicka *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1934, **17**, 618.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 5-Isopropylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (III).—Ethyl α -isopropyladipate (48.8 g.), sodium dust (5.6 g.), and dry benzene (97.6 ml) were refluxed on a water bath till sodium went completely into solution. This was cooled and treated with ice and HCl (conc., 35 ml). The benzene layer was separated and the residue extracted once with benzene. The benzene extract was washed successively with water, dilute sodium carbonate solution, and water. It was dried (CaCl_2) and the solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation provided a colorless oil (27 g.), b.p. 105-108°/4 mm (bath 135-40°). (Found: C, 66.60; H, 9.10. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 66.66; H, 9.09%). It developed an intense violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

2-Ethoxycarbonyl-5-isopropylcyclopentanone-2-ethyl Acetate (IV).—The preceding oxo-ester (41.5 g.) was added to a suspension of sodium dust (4.8 g.) in dry benzene (80 ml) and to the solid sodio salt, cooled in ice, ethyl bromoacetate (24 ml) was added slowly. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and then refluxed gently for 6 hr. The product was cooled, diluted with water, and extracted with benzene. The extract was washed with water, dried, and the solvent removed. The residue was distilled to furnish the ester (IV), b.p. 148-50°/4 mm (bath 170-80°), yield 52 g. (Found: C, 63.32; H, 8.5. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 63.38; H, 8.45%).

Ethyl 5-Isopropylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (V).—The preceding compound (42 g.) was added to a solution formed from sodium (1 g.) and anhydrous ethanol (50 ml). The resulting solution was heated on the water bath for 2½ hr. The residue was cooled, diluted with water, and acidified with 6 N-HCl (16 ml). The oil was separated and the aqueous phase was extracted with ether. The combined extracts were washed with water, dried (CaCl_2), and the solvent was removed. The residue was distilled to provide a colorless oil (40 g.), b.p. 165-68°/4 mm. (Found: C, 61.75; H, 9.05. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 61.8; H, 9.09%).

Ethyl 6-Isopropylcyclohexanone-2,3-dicarboxylate (II).—The preceding ester (20 g.), sodium dust (1.53 g.), and dry benzene (40 ml) were heated on a water bath till sodium went completely into solution. The mixture was cooled, decomposed with ice and 6N-HCl (16 ml). The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous phase was once extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried (CaCl_2), and the solvent evaporated. The residue was distilled to furnish a colorless oil (13.5 g.), b.p. 154°/4 mm. (Found: C, 63.34; H, 8.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 63.38; H, 8.45%). It showed an intense violet colour with ethanolic solution of ferric chloride. The β -oxo-ester (9 g.) on hydrolysis and esterification with ethanolic HCl afforded ethyl 6-isopropylcyclohexanone-3-carboxylate (4.5 g.), b.p. 114-16°/4 mm. (Found: C, 67.8; H, 9.5. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.9; H, 9.43%).

Ethyl 8-Isopropyl-2-oxo-2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10-octahydronaphthalene-5-carboxylate (VI).—The preceding ester (II) (15 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (1.16 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (30 ml). 4-Diethylaminobutan-2-one methiodide, prepared from amino-ketone (8 g.) and methyl iodide (5 ml) in a little of anhydrous ethanol, was added to it slowly. The resulting mixture was allowed to stand overnight and then refluxed gently on a water bath for about 4 hr. The residue was cooled, diluted with water, acidified with

6*N*-HCl (16 ml), and extracted with benzene. The combined benzene extracts were washed successively with water, dilute solution of sodium carbonate, and water. It was dried (CaCl₂) and the solvent evaporated. A mixture of the crude material (21 g.), KOH (28 g.) in water (28 ml), and spirit (84 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 16 hr. The mixture was cooled and ethanol removed; the residue was acidified and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, solvent removed, and the residue dried in a vacuum desiccator. The crude material (11 g.) so obtained was esterified with EtOH·HCl and worked up in the usual way. The main fraction had b.p. 125-30°/4 mm. (Found: C, 72.60; H, 9.10. C₁₆H₂₄O₃ requires C, 72.7; H, 9.09%). Its 2,4-*DNP* formed brick-red plates (from methanol), m.p. 124°. (Found: C, 59.40; H, 6.32. C₂₂H₂₈O₆N₄ requires C, 59.45; H, 6.30%). The quantity obtained was too small.

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